

Deliverable 6.1

Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan

Sofia Mendes, Matteo Sabini, Camila Massri, Esra Akad

Date: 30 July 2024

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan

Document ID	D6.1
Due date	31/07/2024
Submission date	30/07/2024
Dissemination level	Public
Work package	WP 6

Executive summary

This deliverable presents a comprehensive plan of the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities planned for the FoSSNet project, as well as the associated actions to be carried out during the project.

This plan falls under the first task of Work Package (WP) 6: “*Creating impact*”. EUFIC as WP6 leader, in close collaboration with the project coordination team, WP6 task leaders and the entire consortium, is responsible for carefully designing, preparing, and implementing the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities during FoSSNet project lifespan.

Starting from the key actors who will interact with the project during its lifetime – with various levels of engagement – the plan identifies 10 target audiences. They are all addressed by specific communication and dissemination (C&D) activities developed according to their needs and the level of relevance for FoSSNet's scopes and expected impacts.

The plan includes 12 tools and activities: brand identity, a website, a promotional kit, communication through social networks, conferences and events, networking opportunities, and other C&D efforts. Specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been established to monitor and evaluate the activities and overall strategy, allowing the consortium to fine-tune and detail the actions defined in this document to be implemented during the next years and until the end of the project. Moreover, this plan introduces a first version of the exploitation strategy, which will be detailed and consolidated as the project progresses.

This deliverable has the characteristic of being a living document that will be updated throughout the project's duration.

Document information

Project number	101134861
Acronym	FoSSNet
Full name	Pan-European Food Systems Science Network
Project URL	https://fossnet.eu/

Date of delivery	Contractual: 31/07/2024	Actual: 30/07/2024
------------------	-------------------------	--------------------

Authors (name & organisation)	Sofia Mendes (EUFIC)
	Matteo Sabini (EUFIC)
	Camila Massri (EUFIC)
	Esra Akad (EUFIC)

Reviewers (name & organisation)	Technical review	Stine Rosenlund Hansen (RUC)
	Language review	Stine Rosenlund Hansen (RUC)
	Security	NA

Revision history

Issue date	Revision number	Reviewer	Modifications
19/06/2024	V1	John Ingram, Håkan Jönsson, Patricia Homs, Ana Moragues Fau, Efrat Gommeh, Eduardo Urias, Cecilia Tonelli, Mario Roccaro, Ilze Mileiko	Improvements to chapter 2 (Target audiences), messages and vision and mission (chapter 3). Fine-tuning of the tools and activities (chapter 4).
08/07/2024	V2	Mario Roccaro, Maarten van der Kaamper	Improvements to chapter 7 (Exploitation)
25/07/2024	V3	Kelly Rijswijk, Patricia Homs, Stine Rosenlund Hansen	Final quality check by WP leaders and D6.1 contributors

Table of Contents

Executive summary	3
Document information	4
Revision history	5
Index of tables	8
Index of figures.....	8
Abbreviations.....	9
1 Introduction.....	10
1.1 Objective and scope.....	10
2 Target audiences.....	11
2.1 Definition of the target audiences.....	11
2.2 Target audience analysis.....	11
2.2.1 Research performers.....	12
2.2.2 Early career researchers and educators	12
2.2.3 Students in Higher Education	13
2.2.4 Research and Academy Leadership.....	14
2.2.5 Policymakers, their agencies and research-policy initiatives at several levels	14
2.2.6 Existing networks of scientists and science institutions	15
2.2.7 Living Labs	16
2.2.8 EU/national publicly funded projects.....	16
2.2.9 Food systems organisations and networks	17
2.2.10 Investors.....	18
3 FoSSNet Vision & Mission	19
4 Dissemination and communication tools and activities	22
4.1 FoSSNet logo & brand identity	22
4.2 FoSSNet website.....	24
4.2.1 Homepage.....	25
4.2.2 About	26
4.2.3 Network.....	26
4.2.4 News and events	26

Deliverable D6.1

7

4.2.5	Conferences.....	26
4.2.6	Resources.....	27
4.2.7	Getting involved.....	27
4.2.8	Contact.....	27
4.3	Social Networks.....	27
4.3.1	FoSSNet LinkedIn page.....	27
4.3.2	SciFoodHealth LinkedIn and X.....	28
4.4	FoSSNet promotional kit.....	28
4.4.1	Leaflet and Factsheets.....	28
4.4.2	Project standard presentation.....	29
4.5	Press Releases.....	29
4.6	Lay articles.....	29
4.7	External dissemination activities for the FoSSNet project.....	30
4.7.1	Networking activities.....	30
4.7.2	Conferences and events.....	30
4.8	Communities of stakeholders.....	31
4.8.1	Sustainable Food Systems Network.....	31
4.8.2	EIT FoodHive.....	32
4.9	Scientific articles.....	32
4.10	Practice abstracts.....	32
4.11	Policy briefs.....	33
4.12	Podcasts.....	33
5	Key Performance Indicators.....	34
6	Timeline.....	36
7	Exploitation.....	39
7.1	Key Exploitable Results (KERs).....	39
7.2	Exploitation Strategy.....	40
8	FoSSNet DEC management structure and procedures.....	45
8.1	FoSSNet internal management structure.....	45
8.2	Tools and procedures (electronic communications, templates for reporting activities).....	46
9	Conclusion.....	47
	Annex 1: Vision and mission process.....	48

Annex 2: International days..... 51

Annex 3: Conferences & Events relevant for the project..... 52

Index of tables

Table 1: Overview of Key Performance Indicator per communication & dissemination activity.....34

Table 2: Timeline for communication & dissemination activities in Year 1 and Year 2.....36

Table 3: Overview of Key Exploitable results innovation, exploitability and impact.....40

Index of figures

Figure 1: Word cloud with FoSSNet’s core elements mentioned by partners during the co-creation workshop.....Fej

!! Bogmærke er ikke defineret.0

Figure 2: Final version of selected logo.....23

Figure 3: FoSSNet logo design features.....24

Figure 4: Screenshot FoSSNet website homepage.....25

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
CSOs	Civil society organisations
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
ECRs	Early career researchers
FSS	Food Systems Science
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
NGOs	Non-governmental organisations
R&I	Research and innovation
SFSN	Sustainable Food Systems Network
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

FoSSNet aims to establish a long-lasting pan-European academic network for Food Systems Science (FSS), advancing open and inclusive science and education to address the demand for a sustainable transformation. By enhancing and deepening academic networks, FoSSNet seeks to establish an improved Knowledge & Innovation governance structure capable of meeting the emerging challenges of ensuring Europe's nourishment in a healthy, sustainable, and fair manner. FoSSNet's transdisciplinary, inclusive and systemic approach will support the integration of various disciplines and enhance connections and cooperation among food systems scientists, driving collaborative solutions for food systems transformation.

The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) plan outlines the strategy to maximise the impact of the project to increase its visibility and ensure that project outputs are widely disseminated to end-users and relevant target audiences. This plan is meant to be a living document that will be monitored and assessed according to the outlined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). In particular, the FoSSNet DEC plan addresses the following elements:

- **Objectives:** Why are we communicating about the project? What is the goal of our communication activities?
- **Target audiences:** Who does the project aim to reach and speak to?
- **Messages:** What do we want each target audience to hear about FoSSNet?
- **Strategies:** What channels will we use to reach each target group? Which tools will be used?
- **Key Performance Indicators:** How will we measure our impact?

1.1 Objective and scope

The main objective of this plan is to offer partners a set of guidelines, responsibilities, and timelines on how/when/where to communicate, disseminate and exploit the results of the project, as well as to encourage them to use their channels (organisations' websites, social networks, etc.) to support the communication and dissemination activities.

The plan outlines a set of actions in line with the communication strategy. It will help ensure that the following project goals are reached:

- Create the project's identity;
- Generate visibility and awareness for the project, its activities and results during the whole project duration;
- Engage and mobilise stakeholders to establish collaborations and ensure the effective continuation of the FoSSNet network for FSS;
- Empower knowledge and promote networking activities;
- Communicate, disseminate and exploit the project's outcomes successfully.

2 Target audiences

Chapter 2 presents the actors that will interact with FoSSNet throughout the course of the project and define the objective of the interaction and stream of engagement. Moreover, it outlines the messages that will be communicated in the first phase of the project, which will be continuously refined as needed, based on the actual experiences engaging these actors.

2.1 Definition of the target audiences

The detailed information on the target audiences and corresponding messages outlined in this plan have been developed with the contribution of discussions during the in-person FoSSNet Kick-off Meeting (KoM) in April 2024. During this meeting, EUFIC conducted a co-creation workshop where all partners were asked to provide feedback on the definition of the target audiences and key messages to be delivered to each. This interactive session enhanced the DEC plan by clarifying aspects and adding new target audiences such as investors and food systems organisations and networks, which were not part of the Grant Agreement.

Nonetheless, this section should be taken as a preliminary classification of target audiences and may be updated in the next release of the DEC plan (M18) when the role of each actor becomes clearer.

Currently, the FoSSNet target audiences are:

- Research performers
- Early career researchers and educators
- Students in Higher Education
- Research and Academy Leadership
- Policymakers, their agencies and research-policy initiatives at several levels
- Existing networks of scientists and science institutions
- Living labs
- EU/national publicly funded projects
- Food systems organisations and networks
- Investors

2.2 Target audience analysis

In this section, all the target audiences listed before are analysed in detail, describing who they are, what subgroups belong to each audience, and how they will be addressed by FoSSNet activities. It also presents the key messages intended for each group.

2.2.1 Research performers

Who are they? | This group includes researchers from universities (excluding PhD students/candidates and early-stage career researchers), research centres (including NGOs/CSOs), industry research departments, and national science academies across all European Member States and neighbouring countries. They work in different disciplines, such as social sciences and humanities (SSH), food and nutrition, design, engineering, natural and applied sciences, among others.

Reason for being targeted and relation to the project | They are crucial for establishing the FoSSNet network, which aims to develop new methods and tools. The participation of research performers will enhance their and others' research activities through improved inter- and transdisciplinary collaborations, contributing to the food systems transformation in diverse ways.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred to them through the activities of the DEC plan:

- **Collaboration and connectivity:** FoSSNet facilitates collaboration among researchers and research organisations from different scientific disciplines to jointly address food system challenges through a systemic approach.
- **Support and empowerment:** FoSSNet supports research organisations in improving their collaboration with policymakers, providing them with science-based information.
- **Engagement and dialogue:** The project will organise conferences, events, implement a knowledge hub and other initiatives to foster dialogue and exchange of ideas among food systems stakeholders.

2.2.2 Early career researchers and educators

Who are they? | This category includes young food system scientists and professionals with higher education in FSS (MSc or PhD), PhD students/candidates, early-stage career researchers and professionals trained in the field of food systems. Early career professionals primarily refer to educators and teachers working in the private/public sector, including those at Vocational Education and Training (VET) institutions, as well as individuals in relevant positions looking to upskill and reskill their competencies. While most are based in Europe, those from neighbouring and third countries are also targeted to attract the best talents in the European Research Area.

Reason for being targeted and relation to the project | Representing the future research performers, industry representatives, academic leadership and policy makers, they are interested in benefitting from the opportunities offered by the FoSSNet network in terms of improved educational offer, career progression, and access to new data, methods and tools, and their inputs to and participation in the FoSSNet network and activities are crucial to ensure a diverse and inclusive Food System Science.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred to them through the activities of the DEC plan:

- **Community and career opportunities:** FoSSNet provides the chance of becoming part of an epistemic community, gaining access to career opportunities and mentors in FSS.
- **Academic portfolio building:** Enhance your academic portfolio by presenting your research and work at the FoSSNet events and activities.
- **Resource access:** FoSSNet will offer resources (methods, tools, social capital) to boost research impact, both at the societal and scientific level.
- **Empowerment:** FoSSNet empowers young food systems scientists and professionals with the competencies and capabilities for impactful careers (both academic and non-academic).
- **Skill enhancement:** Improve your soft and technical skills by participating in the workshops and summer schools FoSSNet will offer.
- **Interdisciplinary insights:** Gain insights into how your work connects with that of other professionals, explore collaborations, and see how it fits into the bigger picture through FoSSNet's interdisciplinary, transdisciplinary, and systemic approach.

2.2.3 Students in Higher Education

Who are they? | Higher education students (Bachelor and/or Master level) in SSH, including economics, sociology, politics, ethics and law, among others, as well as students in design, engineering and natural and applied sciences related to agricultural, environmental, biological, food and nutrition sciences. Similarly to the previous category, this category includes students based in Europe but also the ones from neighbouring and third countries.

Reason for being targeted and relation to the project | Throughout their learning journey, students will be able to engage and benefit from FoSSNet activities that will enhance their skills and knowledge. Their involvement can lead to innovative solutions and advancements in sustainable practices and policies as well as ensure long-term impact as students carry these values and knowledge into their professional lives.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred to them through the activities of the DEC plan:

- **Curriculum development:** FoSSNet will develop next-generation food system science curricula preparing students for impactful careers.
- **Networking opportunities:** Through FoSSNet, you will be able to connect with a wide network of researchers, professionals and institutions, broadening your knowledge, skills and experience.
- **Future-proof skills:** FoSSNet is creating a future-proof path for building skills in food system science, making it accessible to under and post-grad students, not just senior scientists.

2.2.4 Research and Academy Leadership

Who are they? | University Rectors, prorectors, and deans, directors of research centres and national science academies, including directors of their departments or institutions, covering the same geographical and disciplinary scope as the target group 'Research performers'.

Reason for being targeted and relation to the project | Their support to researchers joining the FoSSNet activities and network is crucial, and they are the ones deciding about the adhesion of their institution to the FoSSNet network and play a key role in defining its governance model for self-sustainable after the end of the FoSSNet project. They are also interested in improving the quality of research, education and knowledge transfer offered by their entities, shaping the next generation of food system scientists and professionals.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred to them through the activities of the DEC plan:

- **Inclusive research practices:** FoSSNet will design and implement methods to support a more inclusive, inter- and transdisciplinary research practice, promoting diversity, gender equality and youth involvement in academia.
- **Competence development:** FoSSNet will contribute to the development of competences on food system science, providing resources, methodologies, and training.
- **Institutional visibility:** Being part of the FoSSNet network will increase your institution's visibility and help attract more students and Food System researchers in early and advanced career-stages.

2.2.5 Policymakers, their agencies and research-policy initiatives at several levels

Who are they? | European (the EC and several of its DGs, the European Parliament and interest groups), International, National level (EU Member States and beyond), regional and local policymakers, as well as the agencies supporting policymakers in the decision-making process, such as JRC, EFSA, EEA, UN agencies (FAO, WHO), among others. This category also includes research-policy initiatives, such as JPI FACCE, JPI HDHL, ERA4HEALTH, all the Horizon Europe Cluster 6 Partnerships (Sustainable Food Systems Partnership, Agroecology Partnership, etc.) BioEast, PRIMA initiative, etc.

Reason for being targeted and relation to the project | They are interested in the definition of innovative governance models to support the food system transition, and in receiving better-quality evidence thanks to the improvement of inter- and transdisciplinary collaboration. This also includes the new methods and tools and the improved impact assessment elaborated thanks to the establishment of the FoSSNet network. Policymakers at both national and European levels can promote the

implementation of transformative food system governance models by leveraging the experience, insights and learnings resulting from the network.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred to them through the activities of the DEC plan:

- **Informing funding strategies:** FoSSNet outcomes will inform funders on how calls and funding schemes can address exclusion mechanisms.
- **Developing effective policies:** The development of effective policies and strategies to address food system challenges will benefit from the understanding of food systems as a dynamic system through FoSSNet's inter- and transdisciplinary approach.
- **Building public trust:** Build public trust and credibility by basing policies on transparent and collaborative research conducted within the FoSSNet project.
- **Enhancing multilevel governance:** FoSSNet will provide policy recommendations on how FSS and science-policy interfaces can improve multilevel food governance.

2.2.6 Existing networks of scientists and science institutions

Who are they? | Research networks of universities, research centres, national science academies at EU level (including the ones established by EU-funded projects like BioBec), international, national and regional level, covering different disciplines relevant to the field of FSS (from biology, nutrition and engineering to ethnography, sociology, economics and law). Examples of such networks include FOODForce, UniAdrion, EFFoST, ISEKI-FOOD, EIT FOOD. This category also includes other networks and initiatives (i.e., on knowledge transfer, innovation, etc.).

Reason for being targeted and relation to the project | They bring essential expertise and skills for ensuring the inter- and transdisciplinarity of the FoSSNet network. Collaborating with these entities can ensure a faster and wider engagement of participants in the FoSSNet network. In addition, they can serve as platforms for exchanging best practices, sharing information on emerging trends and innovations, and identifying opportunities for joint action.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred to them through the activities of the DEC plan:

- **Mobilising academic networks:** FoSSNet will mobilize and engage a variety of academic networks for food system science at EU, national and regional level.
- **Encouraging collective learning:** FoSSNet will offer opportunities for collective learning and reflection, encouraging existing networks to rethink their assumptions, paradigms, and boundaries by adopting systems thinking practices.

2.2.7 Living Labs

Who are they? | Existing and future Living labs operating in different areas (soil, food safety, food policy, agroecology, ICT application to the food sector, etc.), with a particular reference to the ones created under the EU Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe”. They can be reached directly or through their networks, i.e., ENoLL or the SOILL-Startup project.

Reason for being targeted and relation to the project | They can engage a large variety of stakeholders (farmers, innovators, consumers, regional and local communities, local authorities, etc.) in defining transdisciplinary and participatory research activities of the FoSSNet network, contributing to knowledge gaps and priority research needs definition.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred to them through the activities of the DEC plan:

- **Facilitating collaboration:** FoSSNet will offer tools to effectively collaborate with various actors.
- **Influencing research agendas:** For food-related Living Labs, FoSSNet will provide an opportunity to influence research agenda in the food domain.
- **Integrating diverse expertise:** Engaging with FoSSNet to improve the integration of diverse expertise across soil, food safety, agroecology, etc. which will contribute to bridging the gaps between different sectors and disciplines, fostering a systemic approach to food system challenges.
- **Co-creating knowledge:** Collaborating in the co-creation of knowledge by contributing to the definition of research priorities and identifying urgent and emerging knowledge gaps, thus contributing to the relevance and practicality of FoSSNet's research agenda.

2.2.8 EU/national publicly funded projects

Who are they? | Projects funded by Horizon Europe, H2020, as well as by other European or National funding programmes operating in the field of food systems, providing relevant outputs for FoSSNet activities or supporting the project in the uptake of its outputs and in the creation of new collaborations (e.g., CLEVERFOOD, FOODPathS, FOSTER, among others).

Reason for being targeted and relation to the project | To join efforts to increase the expected impacts, through collaborations in specific activities, to successfully engage the stakeholders in the whole process, to liaise with new and more networks they are in contact with, to develop joint communication and dissemination campaigns relevant to the main target audiences.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred to them through the activities of the DEC plan:

- **Supporting cooperation:** FoSSNet will actively support cooperation among researchers working in FSS.
- **Contributing to evidence-based policies:** By sharing best practices, lessons learned and research findings, the collaboration between FoSSNet and other funded-projects will contribute to the development of evidence-based policies and practices, as well as the adoption of innovative solutions for food systems transformation.
- **Collaborating on communication:** FoSSNet seeks to collaborate with other funded-projects on communication activities, to jointly participate in events, align and amplify the outreach of common messages as well as build on each other's results.
- **Connecting and inspiring stakeholders:** The Sustainable Food Systems Networks (SFSN) and the FoSSNet conferences will connect, inspire and engage stakeholders by providing the opportunity to actively exchange knowledge and resources.

2.2.9 Food systems organisations and networks

Who are they? | They are key NGOs, CSOs and stakeholder organisations dedicated to advancing FSS and shaping public policy across Europe. This group includes leading entities like European Technology Platforms (ETP) Food For Life, FoodDrinkEurope, EAT Foundation, Slow Food Europe, and The European Consumer Organisation (BEUC), who work to promote sustainability, raise awareness on food systems, or advocate for consumer rights, and drive innovations in the food sector.

Reason for being targeted and relation to the project | FoSSNet targets these entities to foster collaboration, share knowledge, and co-create solutions that drive sustainable and equitable advancements in food systems. By engaging with them, FoSSNet aims to leverage their expertise and networks to shape effective policies, promote innovative practices, and address the complex challenges of Europe's food systems.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred to them through the activities of the DEC plan:

- **Co-creating knowledge:** Collaborating in the co-creation of knowledge by contributing to the definition of research priorities and identifying urgent and emerging knowledge gaps, thus contributing to the relevance and practicality of FoSSNet's research agenda.
- **Networking and knowledge sharing:** Through FoSSNet, you will be able to connect with a wide network of researchers and institutions, broadening your knowledge and perspectives of current and future challenges and opportunities for your sector.
- **Collective learning and reflection:** FoSSNet will offer opportunities for collective learning and reflection, encouraging food professionals and interest organisations to rethink their assumptions, paradigms, and boundaries by adopting systems thinking practices.

2.2.10 Investors

Who are they? | Privates investors, including business angels, venture capitals, and foundations who are interested in funding research and innovation activities in food systems sector. This group particularly includes those already implementing or seeking to integrate a food systems approach into their investment strategies.

Reason for being targeted and relation to the project | Investors represent a crucial alternative source of funding beyond public grants for food systems research and innovation (R&I) activities. Engaging these investors offers FoSSNet new opportunities for extending R&I proposals, facilitating the development of innovative solutions for sustainable food systems. Additionally, many of these investors have established internal working groups focused on assessing the feasibility and impact of food systems R&I activities, providing valuable models and methodologies that the FoSSNet can learn from and expand upon.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred to them through the activities of the DEC plan:

- **Exploring investment opportunities:** Identifying medium- to long-term investment opportunities in food systems science R&I projects through FoSSNet's comprehensive R&I framework.
- **Access to research-based investment insights:** FoSSNet will offer accessible, research based and updated information about key areas for investing in projects and activities for a sustainable food system.
- **Development of effective investment strategies:** Leverage FoSSNet's inter- and transdisciplinary approach to develop investment strategies that address food system challenges and capitalise on emerging opportunities.
- **Innovating Food Systems through collaboration:** Collaborate with FoSSNet to explore innovative solutions and methodologies that can enhance your investment portfolio and impact.

3 FoSSNet Vision & Mission

This chapter focuses on the project's vision and mission and the process followed to define these statements. The purpose of defining the FoSSNet vision and mission is to establish a common understanding of the project's direction, enabling clear, effective, and jargon-free communication to actors outside of the project. This is particularly relevant in the early stages of FoSSNet to attract interest and build a community of engaged participants.

The vision statement details **where the project aspires to go** and **focuses on tomorrow**, namely on what FoSSNet aims to become. As for the mission statement, it defines the **project's objectives**, and **how it will reach them**. The mission statement **focuses on today** and what the project does to achieve it.

A co-creation workshop was conducted during the in-person KoM with partners in M3 to develop these statements. The information provided in this section is largely based on the outcomes of this workshop. During this occasion, partners worked in groups and followed a three-step exercise, summarized in the scheme below. This exercise was designed to bring partners together to discuss in greater depth the interests, expectations and priorities related to FoSSNet, gathering first the individual perspectives to, subsequently, establish a common ground.

The first step involved reflecting on and identifying the project's core elements. Each partner identified the most relevant elements from their individual perspective and then shared their thoughts with the group. Building on these inputs, partners debated and prioritized which elements should be considered and included in the vision and mission statements. The final step was to integrate the ideas and points discussed into two statements: one for the vision and other for the mission. This exercise culminated

suggested that, ideally, these angles should be combined and integrated in the vision statement. Based on this and in the statements elaborated by the groups, the following proposals for the **vision statement** were developed:

- **Option 1)** Create the next generation of food system thinkers and practitioners and generate new insights, contributing to food systems transformation.
- **Option 2)** Create the next generation of food system thinkers and practitioners to help mainstream systems thinking across academia, business, society and policy by generating new insights that will help transform food systems outcomes for people and planet.
- **Option 3)** FoSSNet envisions the transformation of food systems outcomes for people and planet through systems thinking mainstreaming in academia, society and policy.

As for the mission, partners considered 'system thinking' and 'network' important elements to achieve FoSSNet's objectives and, thus, core elements that should be part of the statement. Two proposals for the **mission statement** were developed:

- **Option 1)** FoSSNet equips policy & practice in food systems through collaborative work and knowledge sharing among system thinkers who are part of a pan-European academic network in food system science and education.
- **Option 2)** FoSSNet equips policy & practice in food systems through the collaborative work and knowledge sharing among researchers and professionals from different disciplines, with diverse perspectives, united in a pan-European network underpinned by systems thinking.

Partners were asked to provide their inputs on the proposals during this document's revision. Considering the different feedback received, for the current stage of the project the following vision and mission statements were selected:

- **Vision** | *Create the next generation of food system thinkers and practitioners to help mainstream systems thinking across academia, business, society and policy by generating new insights that will help transform food systems outcomes for people and planet.*
- **Mission** | *FoSSNet equips policy & practice in food systems through collaborative work and knowledge sharing among system thinkers who are part of a pan-European academic network in food system science and education.*

These will serve as basis for future discussions and will be revised and improved throughout the course of the project.

4 Dissemination and communication tools and activities

The achievement of the objectives of this plan will be ensured by the complementarity of its activities and thanks to the use of different tools and channels aimed at addressing identified stakeholders' needs and expectations. In this chapter, the tools used, and the activities implemented are presented in detail. Each of them will be designed in compliance with the HorizonEurope guidelines to acknowledge the funding received from the EU:

- [Communicating about your EU-funded project](#)

In the next paragraphs, each tool or activity is described, indicating the next steps, the FoSSNet partner responsible for the implementation and how the other ones will be involved in them. The tools and activities identified are the following:

- Brand Identity
- Website
- Social Networks
- FoSSNet promotional kit
- Press releases
- Lay articles
- External dissemination activities
- Communities of stakeholders
- Scientific articles
- Practice abstracts
- Policy briefs
- Podcasts

4.1 FoSSNet logo & brand identity

The FoSSNet brand identity is based on recognizable elements of a brand (e.g. - brand color, logo, name, symbol) that allow the target audience to identify the brand. Therefore, the logo is one of the key elements of the project identity, which aims to effectively represent the vision, mission and core objectives of the FoSSNet project. As the project follows an inter- and transdisciplinary approach, the logo and its key element have been co-designed by the whole consortium, considering different perspectives, in a process coordinated by EUFIC.

Prior to the online KoM meeting, EUFIC conducted a survey among all partners to gather their opinions on some elements that characterize the design of a logo (messages it should carry, preferred shape and colors, etc.). Based on the survey results, two

options were developed and shared with partners during the online KoM (February 7, 2024), including the concept behind each logo and mock-ups showing how they would appear on communication materials. After all partners voted on their preferred option with further comments for improvement, the following final version was selected:

Figure 2: Final version of selected logo

The creation of the logo was inspired by a **sliced onion**:

- Its distinct layers represent the **multifaceted, holistic nature of food systems**;
- The growing pattern from the center of the onion outward, representing the **continuous growth of the network**;
- The translucent quality of an onion, symbolizing the **transparency and clear communication** between all members of the network;
- Peeling back the layers of an onion reveals its core, as the network aims to **uncover essential insights and knowledge about sustainable and resilient food systems**.

See Figure 3 below for the features of logo.

Figure 3: FoSSNet logo design features

EUFIC's graphic design team has created a brand manual to guide partners and external users (e.g. web developers) in the correct use of the logo and its elements. The document is available to all partners on the internal project SharePoint platform ([here](#)) and shows the different versions of the logo to be used, the specific font, colors and dimensions, as well as examples of the logo's application on different materials.

4.2 FoSSNet website

The website is the entry point and the primary information source of the FoSSNet project, informing about its scopes, activities, partners, news, events and results, and it will be connected to the project's channels and media (i.e. FoSSNet LinkedIn page, SciFoodHealth social media accounts, and SFSN).

EUFIC coordinated the website creation process, taking care of the WP leaders' needs and requirements, and was responsible for the technicalities, including the selection of a supplier for the website technical development, and content creation in collaboration with project partners.

As a first step, EUFIC, bought the domain <https://www.fossnet.eu/> and defined the first structure for the website. Three potential suppliers were asked for quotations and provided their best offers. After the evaluation of offers, at the end of March 2024, EUFIC selected BoostU as the supplier for the FoSSNet website.

According to the contract, the website is being developed using WordPress as Content Management Systems (CMS), preferred to the customised ones because of its open-source nature. The FoSSNet website is hosted on the EUFIC servers, that are based in the EU (France). According to the contract signed with BoostU, the website will be maintained alive for three years after the end of the project (till January 2031): during this period, the company will update the installed plug-ins, monitor the security and maintain the Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) certificate, thus allowing users to browse the website without any issues.

EUFIC prepared the design and framework for the website structure after consulting various project partners. The content of each page and section was produced by EUFIC with the contribution of FoSSNet partners, and additional feedback was asked once the design and structure of the website were finalised. EUFIC was responsible for the last fine-tuning of the texts provided and for their uploading on the website. The FoSSNet website (Deliverable 6.2) was launched in Month 5 (June 2024).

The website will be updated on a regular basis with the project's updates, lay articles, details about the FoSSNet conferences and relevant events, public deliverables, scientific publications, and other communication materials. The website structure and featured sections are described below.

4.2.1 Homepage

It represents the entry point of the website, containing simple and attractive messages for the identified target audiences to engage them in the project activities. Designed to guarantee users' accessibility and in line with the visibility standards, it will:

- connect the users to the other website resources, tools and sections;
- show in brief the project description (linking to a more detailed page) and the three main pillars of the project;
- show in brief the conferences organised by the project;
- show in brief the latest news and next events;
- re-address the users to other project's channels (FoSSNet LinkedIn, SciFoodHealth LinkedIn & X, and SFSN);
- give the possibility to subscribe for receiving news and information on FoSSNet results and activities (newsletter created by EUFIC and operated via Brevo tool);
- give the possibility to contact using the FoSSNet generic email;
- inform the user about the cookies policy (giving it the possibility to choose the options in compliance with the current legislation) and know more about the policy privacy policy (prepared by RUC);
- acknowledge the project funding.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the FoSSNet website - Homepage

4.2.2 About

This section will provide the main information on the project, showing:

- fundamental information about FoSSNet (project overview, goals and approach);
- members of the consortium, with a logo and brief description of each partner (including their role in the project) and other information (i.e. partner website, staff involved in the project, contacts, etc.);
- linked networks and/or projects in collaboration with their logo and descriptions (e.g FoodPaths, Cleverfood, Foster, Foodclick, FutureFoods);
- explanation on contribution to Food 2030 Governance pathway;
- the FoSSNet Advisory board and its members, including each one's picture, the logo of the entity they represent and a short biography.

4.2.3 Network

This section will provide functional information related to the network including,

- description of the network;
- information on how to join the network;
- explanation on the benefits of joining;
- an interactive map to present entities that will be developed at a later stage, after the website launch.

Currently, this page provides general information about the network.

4.2.4 News and events

In this section, all the news and upcoming events interesting for all the defined target audiences are shown in detail, including information on both the past and upcoming events. This page is connected to the preview available on the FoSSNet homepage.

4.2.5 Conferences

This section will provide detailed information on upcoming conferences organised by the consortium, including the presentation of each conference, related news and resources. The Conferences page is also connected to the preview available on the FoSSNet website.

4.2.6 Resources

This section will include the materials and outputs (leaflet, reports, policy briefs, factsheets, among others) produced by the project which will be continuously added as they are developed during FoSSNet's lifespan.

4.2.7 Getting involved

This section will include practical information on main activities in which external stakeholders can be involved and where they can find relevant information about the key activities implemented by FoSSNet, such as:

- Results of the analysis of the food systems education systems;
- Summer Schools and Hackathons;
- Results of the FoSSNet research activities (e.g., on the true cost of food).

Since it is based on activities that will be implemented during a later stage of the project, this section is available only in a basic version and it will be constantly updated integrated.

4.2.8 Contact

This page will show users how to get in touch with the FoSSNet project, namely a contact form (responses sent to the email info@fossnet.eu).

4.3 Social Networks

Capitalising on the established presence of the EUFIC-managed SciFoodHealth channels and other partner organisations' channels, FoSSNet aims to conduct communication activities to reach its wide target audience. All social media posts will consistently include the project hashtag (#FoSSNet) for easy statistics tracking, wherever possible forward to the project website, and invite to subscribe to the project's newsletter.

4.3.1 FoSSNet LinkedIn page

As the consortium aims to establish a pan-European academic network of FSS, a FoSSNet LinkedIn (@FoSSNet) account was preferred as fit. It aims to reach and engage with a wider target audience and provide them with project-related information and a chance to be a part of the network. This page's contents will include the introduction of the project, namely its scope and main objectives, highlight the relevance of such

project considering the current panorama of Europe's food system and introduce the partner organisations involved in the project. It will also create a space for networking among the interested entities. Additionally, this page will serve as a platform to share updates on the project's activities and communicate the outputs, by giving an overview of the information people can expect to find in the documents produced (e.g. reports, policy briefs, factsheets, etc.) to encourage people to check the full documents and attract traffic to the project's website.

The FoSSNet LinkedIn page was launched in April 2024, under the name FoSSNet, and it is being managed by EUFIC. As of today (17 July 2024) the page has 196 followers and 13 posts shared.

4.3.2 SciFoodHealth LinkedIn and X

To increase visibility, communicate results and direct traffic to the FoSSNet website and LinkedIn page, the SciFoodHealth LinkedIn and X accounts (current reach of >28.000 followers) will be used. The SciFoodHealth accounts are managed by EUFIC team who is also responsible for creating and sharing contents about the FoSSNet project. All social media posts will include the project hashtag (#FoSSNet) for easy statistics tracking.

4.4 FoSSNet promotional kit

To support the dissemination and communication of the project and provide audiences with an overview of the FoSSNet main objectives and results, a promotional kit will be created. The kit will consist of a leaflet, factsheets, a general presentation of the project and press releases (the latter are described in detail in point 4.5).

4.4.1 Leaflet and Factsheets

To give an overview of the FoSSNet main objectives and results, a leaflet and factsheets will be produced at different stages of the project, according to the achievements reached. In particular, a first leaflet will be designed and produced by EUFIC with partners' contributions at an early stage of the project (July 2024) to explain the project's scope, main activities and present the consortium. Additional leaflets may be produced later in the project according to the WP requests and needs, mainly to engage specific target audiences. In any case, RUC and WP leaders are responsible for the text draft definition, meanwhile, EUFIC develops their graphic design.

Leaflets and factsheets will be disseminated during events, via social media and newsletters and, to reduce the environmental impact, these will be available mainly in a digital version on the FoSSNet website.

4.4.2 Project standard presentation

All FoSSNet partners are encouraged to present the project, their activities and results in seminars, public hearings, meetings, conferences and other relevant events, with the objectives to inform the target audiences and engage them, promote the project activities and their exploitation, contribute to the establishment of collaborations. Considering this, a standard presentation of the project is being prepared by EUFIC with contributions from WPs and will be made available to all partners in FoSSNet SharePoint.

4.5 Press Releases

Press releases will be developed to raise awareness and inform the media about the project's main activities, developments and outcomes. Thanks to this tool, more stakeholders are expected to be reached. Press releases (at the national and European levels) can target both generic and specialized media, according to the main content of it. In any case, the press release targeting generic media and the large public are being developed avoiding scientific jargon; differently from the one targeting specialized media.

EUFIC is responsible for composing the first draft version in English of each press release, which is then shared with the coordinator and other relevant partners (i.e., the WP responsible for the activities presented in the press release). When ready, the press release is sent by EUFIC to journalists and media representatives selected according to their relevance to the topic and via the media platform AlphaGalileo; moreover, the document will be also shared with all partners, inviting them to send it to their contacts through their press offices and conducting a translation, if required. Finally, press releases will be made downloadable on the project website and promoted on the FoSSNet LinkedIn page and SFSN.

Throughout the project's lifespan, three press releases are planned to be developed. The first press release was shared on Month 4 (May 2024) giving an overview of the project's activities, ambition, and its relevance within the context of Europe Day celebrations (9 May).

4.6 Lay articles

Short articles in simple and non-technical language exploring FoSSNet's key concepts, such as 'food system science' and 'systems thinking', will be produced and made available on the project's website and promoted in the social networks. These articles are aimed at non-academic audiences interested in the topic of food systems to help understand the project's work, approach and its relevance in order to facilitate their

engagement with FoSSNet, increase the project's outreach and raise awareness on food systems transformation.

4.7 External dissemination activities for the FoSSNet project

4.7.1 Networking activities

Led by EUFIC and supported by partners, particularly WP2, a catalogue will be drafted with potential synergies for communication, dissemination, and exploitations activities, and other potential collaboration with and between stakeholders, projects, initiatives, and networks. The mutual benefits that could arise from the cooperation will be outlined together with a timeline for contacting these entities. Some of the collaboration opportunities will consist in participating in webinars, workshops, campaigns organised by other WPs, among others. The collaborations will be established with initiatives such as FOODPathS (for connecting with the Network of Universities on Sustainable Food Systems), the Horizon EU National Contact Points (NCPs) network projects (i.e., Care4Bio for Cluster 6, MSCA-NET, WIDERA.NET), or involving NCPs in trainings for researchers - MSCA alumni network, BIObec (to cooperate with networks of universities working in bioeconomy).

4.7.2 Conferences and events

FoSSNet will organise three interlinked conferences during the project's lifetime and an additional event will be held in Warsaw, focusing on expanding the network in Eastern Europe. These events will serve as a forum for sharing knowledge and ideas, empowering all stakeholders, and contributing to the achievement of the project objectives.

The first conference will be in Oxford in 2025, move to Lund in 2026, and culminate in Brussels in 2027. Each conference will build upon the outcomes of the previous one, creating a cohesive and comprehensive dialogue on the development and implementation of food system science.

Oxford 2025 will set the stage by defining a common language and conceptual framework, based on initial network mapping and social network analysis.

Lund 2026 will expand on these foundations, bringing in diverse research approaches and focusing on the development of practical capabilities and tools.

Brussels 2027 will consolidate the insights from Oxford and Lund, translating them into actionable recommendations for policymakers and other stakeholders.

The FoSSNet conferences will include presentations and joint discussion of abstracts and papers, facilitating knowledge production and fostering collaboration.

Additionally, FoSSNet partners will participate in external events and conferences with different aims according to the participating audiences. These events provide an opportunity to present results and engage new potential actors. A list of relevant events and conferences are continuously shared thanks to the collaboration of all FoSSNet partners, via the internal reporting scheme shared with the partners. This will include both international/European and national events.

4.8 Communities of stakeholders

4.8.1 Sustainable Food Systems Network

The Sustainable Food Systems Network (SFSN) is an online community dedicated to people interested in sharing knowledge, building new partnerships and collaborations, being informed on the latest news, and finding opportunities in the field of food systems. Launched in 2021 by the FIT4FOOD2030 project, managed and animated by EUFIC, the community counts with >2.300 members representing policy makers, entrepreneurs, researchers, NGO representatives, citizens, students, and others interested in being engaged in food systems. The discussion is organised on the food system at glance, as well as in thematic groups: currently one active on the microbiome, run by the cluster of projects “Microbiome4Life”, and a second one on engaging citizens in the food systems transformation (which is run by CLEVERFOOD project). The platform has dedicated sections to:

- facilitate the exchange of knowledge about food systems, called “Resources”;
- promote events and invite other users to join them;
- opportunities for a wide range of collaborations (job offers, mentorship, internships, etc.).

Each member of the community can publish posts (such as a social network), upload items in the Resources section, launch surveys, quizzes, polls, and promote opportunities, among others.

Given its characteristics, **the SFSN community serves as an ideal channel to connect and engage with specific audiences for the FoSSNet activities, and the wider community interested in the topic. FoSSNet partners are called to be as interactive as possible in the SFSN**, by posting on regular basis. The posts can include their personal views on topics related to food systems, but also information about the project, its progression, publishing results, and news, promoting events and other communication campaigns, and launching consultations/polls, among others. When posting information about the project, partners will be asked to include the hashtag of the project in the post (#FoSSNet).

The SFSN has the advantage of being able to be used as a repository, which is particularly useful for the exploitation of important outputs of the projects even after the project ends. As previously mentioned, the platform allows members to create events, which will be automatically sent to the whole community via email and added to their calendars. This proactive feature allows us to keep the community updated without investing any additional effort or time.

In the case of FoSSNet, it is the perfect way to find and understand the interest of our target audiences and it is necessary to promote activities in the network that include them, such as workshops where everyone participates and feels part of the "network" and can give their opinion. The objective of having selected the SFSN as a channel is to continue building a network that can provide direct feedback, can benefit and help to shape the FSS taking into consideration the views of all the disciplines involved in it.

4.8.2 EIT FoodHive

EIT FoodHIVE is an online membership community platform where individuals and organisations from the broader EIT Food community can connect and share with each other. Through this platform, EIT Food community will have access to news, events, updates and activities developed under FoSSNet and will be a space to promote the discussion and dialogue between members.

4.9 Scientific articles

FoSSNet partners will co-author joint scientific articles to disseminate project's outputs enhancing FSS and maximize impact. These will be submitted to scientific journals, for example: Nature Food; Food Policy; Agricultural Systems; Agriculture & Human Values; European Review of Agricultural Economics; Social and Technological Change among others. FoSSNet will provide open access (OA) to peer-reviewed scientific articles.

4.10 Practice abstracts

FoSSNet will summarise the main results into short and easy-to-read documents, using the EIP-AGRI Common Format, and uploading them into the [EIP-AGRI Platform](#), thus ensuring a wider dissemination of results and increasing the exploitation opportunities. The topics of the Practice Abstracts will be defined in line with the specific strategy defined by the Exploitation Plan and on the basis of the identified Key Exploitable Results (KERs, see chapter 7.1). In total, at least 14 Practice Abstracts will be submitted.

4.11 Policy briefs

During the project lifetime, policy briefs based on the project results and findings will be developed by the FoSSNet partners to inform policy and regulation for food systems transformation. In specific, three policy briefs produced by the University of Barcelona will focus on how FSS and science policy interfaces can support the improvement of multilevel food system governance. These will be targeted to three levels of governance: local/regional, national and European to provide guidance to strengthen the international science policy interface for improved global food system governance.

The policy briefs will be made publicly available on the FoSSNet website and promoted on the FoSSNet LinkedIn and SciFoodHealth social media accounts.

4.12 Podcasts

To ensure all communication formats are covered, audio content in the shape of podcasts will be created. The podcast will consist of at least four episodes that will promote the project's outputs. The podcast format will consist of a dialogue or interviews carried out by a moderator and an invited expert from the consortium. Each podcast will be conducted in English language and episodes will be available on the EIT Food podcast channel and transcribed into articles that will be uploaded to the FoSSNet website. The content of the podcasts will be developed by project partners directly involved in the topic to be addressed, while EUFIC supports and facilitates their development, promotion and dissemination. The practical implementation of podcasts will be further defined in a later stage and described in detail during the second version of this document (expected for July 2025), considering the results achieved, the target needs, and possible suggestions collected from the FoSSNet network and Advisory Board.

5 Key Performance Indicators

A set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were fixed to assess the implementation of the plan every 12 months. In addition to the evaluation, KPIs will enable partners to correct and re-address the strategy, considering also new emerging needs, external factors affecting the project and experience gained by the FoSSNet consortium in implementing foreseen activities. KPIs are built considering the ones contained in the Grant Agreement and new ones introduced in the first months of the project.

Table 1: Overview of Key Performance Indicator per communication & dissemination activity

Tools, channel activities	Metrics method	Expected results
Website	Number of website views and countries reached	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Total page views: >15.000 - Countries reached: >20
Social Networks	Number of posts, impressions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of posts: >120 - An average total reach of >10.000 impressions in the FoSSNet LinkedIn page and the SciFoodHealth accounts
FoSSNet promotional kit: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leaflet and other resources (factsheets, press releases, etc.) 	Number of kits and downloads	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promotional kits produced: >1 - >500 downloads in total
Press Releases	Number of press releases, journalists contacted and downloads	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of press releases distributed: at least 3 - No. of journalists contacted (direct email): >100 - Downloads: >50

SFSN	Number of posts and news in the newsletter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of posts: >15 - News in the newsletter: >40
Lay articles	Number of articles produced and published on FoSSNet and partners websites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of lay articles: at least 15
Liaison with networks, projects & initiatives	Number of activities implemented and actors engaged	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaborations established with No. projects & initiatives: >30
Conferences and events	Number of project presentations given by partners at local/national/EU/international events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FoSSNet presentation in external conferences and events: at least 20
Scientific articles	Number of scientific articles submitted or published by one or several partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of articles submitted: >15
Practice abstracts	Number of practice abstracts produced and uploaded to the EIP-AGRI portal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of practice abstracts: >12
Policy briefs	Number of policy briefs produced and published on FoSSNet website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of policy briefs released: >11
EIT FoodHive	Number of posts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of posts: >45
Podcasts in the EIT Food channel and transcribed into articles	Number of episodes and listeners (per episode)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of episodes made available: >3 - No. of listeners: at least 100

6 Timeline

In this chapter, a timeline for all WP6 related activities expected to be implemented throughout the first two years of the FoSSNet project is provided. The table below presents only the main activities to be implemented, while the daily ones (such as posts on social networks and website news articles) are not considered, since they will take place all along the project lifetime. This table will be updated with the revision of this document.

Table 2: Timeline for communication & dissemination activities in Year 1 and Year 2

Year - 2024					
Month	Communication & dissemination activities				Meetings
February		FoSSNet logo co-creation and selection			Online Kick-off meeting
March		FoSSNet brand manual and templates (.ppt, .doc, Teams background, etc.)		Definition of the website requirements and selection of the website supplier	
April	FoSSNet Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (D6.1)		FoSSNet LinkedIn page launch	Website design development and content preparation	In person Kick-off meeting and co-creation workshop on target audiences, messages, vision and mission statements
May		1 st Press Release			Meeting with WP leaders
June				Website launch	Meeting with the organisation committee for the 1 st FoSSNet

					Conference (Oxford)
July		1 st version FoSSNet promotional toolkit (with the leaflet and rollup)			Meeting with the organisation committee for the 1 st FoSSNet Conference (Oxford)
August				Article about the FoSSNet promotional toolkit	Meeting with WP leaders
September					Internal workshop to present the FoSSNet promotional toolkit
October			Promotion of the 1 st FoSSNet Conference (Oxford)		
November				Lay article about FoSSNet's key concepts	
December					

Year - 2025

Month	Communication & dissemination activities			Meetings
January		Preparation of practice abstracts for EIP-AGRI	Promotion of the 1 st FoSSNet Conference (Oxford)	Meeting with the organisation committee for the 1 st FoSSNet Conference (Oxford)
February				Lay article about FoSSNet's key concepts

March		1 st FoSSNet Conference (Oxford)			
April	Review of the FoSSNet Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (D6.1)	Planning and preparation of FoSSNet scientific articles		Article about the 1 st FoSSNet Conference (Oxford)	
May				Lay article about FoSSNet's key concepts	
June					
July	First update of the DEC Plan (D6.1)	2 nd Press Release			
August				Lay article about FoSSNet's key concepts	
September		Awareness campaign on food systems approach			
October					
November					
December				Lay article about FoSSNet's key concepts	

7 Exploitation

The dissemination and communication efforts outlined are strategically aimed at maximizing FoSSNet exploitation opportunities to ensure the achievement of the project's expected outcomes and impacts. Planning and developing a comprehensive strategy for the exploitation activity is crucial to ensure long-term sustainability and use of FoSSNet's results beyond the project duration and European Commission funding. However, it is essential to note that this plan is delivered early in the project (July 2024) when no results are available. Therefore, this chapter should be considered a guide for future activities planned in greater detail. Before the conclusion of FoSSNet, partners must collectively assess the validity and relevance of the measures defined and address eventual Intellectual Property Rights issues to be treated with some exemption from the Consortium Agreement prescriptions. Additionally, two deliverables dedicated exclusively to the FoSSNet exploitation pathways will be produced in **July 2026** and updated later by the end of the project, **January 2028**, where the exploitation strategy will be described in detail.

Acknowledging this, the current exploitation plan is designed to define the Key Exploitable Results (KERs in section 7.1) that FoSSNet will produce, and a strategy is proposed (in section 7.2).

7.1 Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

As stated by the European Commission, a KER is “[...] an identified main interesting result which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive benefits – downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education”.¹

As a first step to kickstart the exploitation process, it is essential to identify among the various project results the ones most promising in terms of exploitability, degree of innovation and impact. A preliminary list of KERs has been defined in close collaboration with partners. This will be revised later when results will be effectively achieved. So far, the identified KERs are the following:

- Conceptual framework for advancing food system transition science, system boundaries and scientific boundaries
- Guide to processes for food system transformation
- Visualisation tool for the EU food system
- EU Food System Map
- Map visualizing the locus and relations of food system scientists

¹ European IP Helpdesk – Horizon Europe Bulletin, No.4, 2021, p.10 (<https://horizoneurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/Horizon-Europe-Helpdesk-Bulletin-2021.pdf>)

- Established, dynamic self-organising network
- Methodological blueprint and indicator set for inclusive interdisciplinary research
- Participatory research methodology for open food system science linked to the science-practitioner-policy interface
- Policy recommendations on how food systems science and science policy interfaces can improve food system governance
- New curricula for food system science for PG and professional courses
- Capacity building curriculum for early career researchers and professionals
- Dedicated communication strategy for wide stakeholder engagement
- Meeting programme

7.2 Exploitation Strategy

FoSSNet's exploitation strategy has been designed to enhance the project's impact. All partners will be intensely involved in these activities, providing relevant inputs for the project's success.

The overall approach for the KERs is to prioritise their mobilisation to ensure the FoSSNet network will be maintained and will be able to continue producing value for research and policy. As such, the aim is to secure the long-term sustainability of the network as a key research infrastructure and a durable interlocutor for policymakers, industry, academia and civil society. Financial sustainability mechanisms are introduced to ensure that the network can remain an open community and that open access to its resources is secured.

The second aim of the exploitation strategy is to ensure key tools and assets are brought into circulation so that they can generate societal benefits and act as important inputs to policy, further research, and education. System maps and developed curricula will be shared among FoSSNet's beneficiaries and beyond.

Table 3 below analyses each KER identified before according to their innovation, exploitability, and impact upon successful exploitation. The number of each KER refers to the WP in which it will be generated.

Table 3: Overview of Key Exploitable results innovation, exploitability and impact

KER	Innovation	Exploitability	Impact
<p>KER 1a: Conceptual framework for advancing food system transition science, system boundaries and scientific boundaries</p>	<p>Novel approach to incorporating all relevant sciences into food systems transitions – a method to create a shared knowledge space where boundary objects (e.g. KER 1c) enable different communities of practice to engage in mutual sense-making.</p>	<p>Will be exploited through the network (KER 2b) and the policy advice (KER 4b).</p>	<p>Transformative as it creates a common language between different sciences AND policymakers, meaning that research can translate more directly into impact pathways.</p>
<p>KER 1b: Guide to processes for food system transformation</p>	<p>New processes to examine outcomes and trade-offs for transformation processes to enable stakeholders to jointly work in the food system space (FOKIS).</p>	<p>Will be exploited through the network (KER 2) and the experiments that will inform KER 4b.</p>	<p>Transformative as it contributes to the common language between different sciences AND policymakers and helps to operationalize food system thinking.</p>
<p>KER 1c: Visualisation tool for the EU food system</p>	<p>Novel tool to support effective visualisation of systems, their dynamics and boundaries – a boundary object (Star and Griesemer 1989) to enable different communities of practice to contribute to the shared knowledge and discuss options for change (KER 1a).</p>	<p>Will be exploited through the network (KER 2b), the policy advice (KER 4b) and the communication strategy (KER 6a).</p>	<p>Enhances accessibility to food system configurations for analysis, participative research approaches and policy making.</p>
<p>KER 1d: EU Food System Map</p>	<p>The food system map will bring together the key information and data to characterise</p>	<p>Will serve as a basis for identification of transformation needs by the network, the</p>	<p>Provides a common understanding of the current EU food system configuration</p>

	<p>how the EU is currently ensuring food security and what some of the implications are for the environmental footprint, economic contribution and social impacts.</p>	<p>EC and other stakeholders and for use in communication strategy.</p>	<p>and bottlenecks, enables joint problem analysis by different stakeholders.</p>
<p>KER 2a: Map visualizing the locus and relations of food system scientists</p>	<p>Map of network relations (within/between academic centres, food innovation hubs, academic networks) among all relevant scientists and research organisations (HEIs, networks, RTOs).</p>	<p>Basis for matchmaking mechanisms of scientists and institutions, for networking with other disciplines, for revealing the expansion of the science field.</p>	<p>Enhanced visibility of FSS and transitions approaches among policymakers, academic institutions and networks and media.</p>
<p>KER 2b: Established, dynamic self-organising network</p>	<p>Bringing relevant research organisations (HEIs, networks, RTOs) into a self-organising network fostering a common understanding of the domain (KER 1a), providing collaboration spaces for interdisciplinary research underpinned by KER 3, a resource for accessing expertise, and an official entity for policy dialogue and funding coordination.</p>	<p>Basis for financial sustainability mechanisms such as funding, membership fees, sponsorship, consultancy fees.</p>	<p>Enhanced visibility of FSS and transitions approaches among policymakers, academic institutions and networks and media, plus enhanced collaborations among members.</p>
<p>KER 3: Methodological blueprint and indicator set for inclusive interdisciplinary research</p>	<p>No specific resources exist on quality criteria, process requirements and indicators supporting inclusive inter- and transdisciplinary research for food</p>	<p>This will be a key resource for the network (KER 2b), and as an open tool provides a template that other domains may adopt.</p>	<p>Ensures that the integration of humanities and social sciences, gender, geography, ethnicity and other diversity dimensions are adequately addressed</p>

	<p>system. Methodological blueprint and indicator set provide a key tool for principles of inclusive interdisciplinary research for food system transition.</p>		<p>within the knowledge space.</p>
<p>KER 4a: Participatory research methodology for open food system science linked to the science-practitioner-policy interface</p>	<p>This provides a key resource for researchers and policymakers to support food system transitions in academic and practitioner contexts.</p>	<p>This methodology will be made available for free as a toolkit. The consortium can monetise training on how to use it.</p>	<p>The tested methodology provides a common language (KER 1a) to support research and policymaking.</p>
<p>KER 4b: Policy recommendations on how food systems science and science policy interfaces can improve food system governance</p>	<p>Experimentation in specific science-practitioner-policy interfaces will contribute to the development of three policy briefs on how FSS can support effective policy and decision-making and strengthen science-policy interfaces for improved multilevel food governance.</p>	<p>As a resource, these policy recommendations will be made available through the communication strategy (KER 6a).</p>	<p>The policy briefs will be targeted at three levels of governance: local/regional, national, and European, to provide guidance on strengthening the international science policy interface for improved global food system governance.</p>
<p>KER 5a: New curricula for food system science for PG and professional courses</p>	<p>While several FSS curricula are available, most are limited in scope. The new curricula provide a fully up-to-date approach based on a shared conceptualisation (KER 1a), visualisation tool (KER 1c), and food system map (KER 1d).</p>	<p>The curriculum can be offered as a free resource to interested HEIs and VET schools. The consortium can monetise train-the-trainer events.</p>	<p>The new curricula will help equip the new generation of change agents in the food system with a common language and approach, strengthening individual careers and the policy and research spaces.</p>

<p>KER 5b: Capacity building curriculum for early career researchers and professionals</p>	<p>This curriculum provides early career researchers and professionals with key employability, entrepreneurship and leadership skills in an integrated approach to ensure employability for both academic and non-academic career paths.</p>	<p>The curriculum can be offered for free to HEIs and VET schools. The consortium can monetise train-the-trainer events. Non-academic partners will be offered via FoSSNet network activities.</p>	<p>Enhanced efficacy and entrepreneurial mindset and skills in the pool of FSS space.</p>
<p>KER 6a: Dedicated communication strategy for wide stakeholder engagement</p>	<p>A key resource for all actors in food system transition space (KER 2b) to communicate effectively with stakeholders through the conceptualisation (KER 1a), visualisation tool (KER 1c) and food system map (KER 1d).</p>	<p>This strategy can be used by all actors in the research and policy spaces; it will be provided as a free resource.</p>	<p>This helps build a common language and approach throughout and beyond the network (KER 2b) towards all relevant stakeholders.</p>
<p>KER 6b: Meeting programme</p>	<p>The conferences, supported by presence at annual events creates a new platform for the scientific community to convene, collaborate and engage with stakeholders.</p>	<p>Basis for financial sustainability mechanisms such as sponsorship and entrance fees.</p>	<p>Essential way for the research community to meet, collaborate and debate research priorities with policy makers, industry and civil society.</p>

8 FoSSNet DEC management structure and procedures

All FoSSNet partners will be actively involved in implementing the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities under the EUFIC's coordination. Moreover, EUFIC will collect data and monitor KPIs to involve partners in the revision and fine-tuning of the strategy. In any case, partners are expected to contribute to the following actions:

- Implementing communication, dissemination and exploitation activities within the networks they belong to, in their own countries and at the European level;
- Engaging stakeholders belonging to the identified target audiences in a meaningful and coordinated way;
- Mapping events and providing news and updates for the FoSSNet website and social media;
- Participating in a coordinated way at conferences, workshops, events, etc. to promote the project and its outcomes;
- Requesting support for communication and dissemination materials (flyers, save the date for events, factsheets, etc.) proactively and on time;
- Keeping track of all activities implemented, aimed to show the consortium outreach and address the expected outcomes and impacts planned.

8.1 FoSSNet internal management structure

EUFIC, WP6 leader, is responsible for the overall management and support of the activities defined under this plan, with the support of EIT Food (as a partner responsible for the exploitation activities), RUC (as a coordinator) and the other WP leaders (that will ensure the contribution of all partners and specifically for supporting the activities to be implemented under their WPs). In order to ensure this coordination, a discussion point dedicated to C&D activities will be inserted in any Executive Board meeting, or, in alternative when there is a specific need, with the organisation of ad hoc meetings in which WP leaders and any other relevant partner are invited. **EUFIC will be responsible for preparing the topics to be discussed during the Executive Board meetings and to organise the additional meetings, if necessary** (selecting a date and timeslot, sending the agenda and the link for connecting, taking notes, preparing minutes, etc.).

In addition to this and when relevant, EUFIC will contact directly all or some partners, according to the purpose, i.e., to update on outstanding results or activities, ask for support in the promotion of specific campaigns, request information needed for the

implementation of the provisions contained in this plan, etc. To ease the process, EUFIC asked FoSSNet partners to provide the contacts of the people working in their press offices (available in SharePoint, on a dedicated page within the spreadsheet in the [“Contact List” section](#)), to be engaged only when necessary.

8.2 Tools and procedures (electronic communications, templates for reporting activities)

All FoSSNet partners are required to keep track of their communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, with a twofold aim:

- Monitor the activities implemented through the KPIs (and provide a timely assessment of the provisions contained in this plan)
- Tracking the outreach and assessing the achievement of the expected outcomes and impacts.

EUFIC prepared a reporting scheme integrated into the FoSSNet SharePoint ([Reporting communication and dissemination activities](#)), allowing all partners to continuously report about the activities performed and the results reached. The structure and the instructions on how to use it will be presented in a video recorded by EUFIC and available to partners on SharePoint. Moreover, EUFIC is sending monthly reminders to partners asking to fill in the online reporting form (as well as to keep them informed with the latest updates).

In principle, FoSSNet partners should enter data in SharePoint as soon as they implement an activity. EUFIC will monitor the process and, in any case, it will contact all partners reminding them of their duties:

- Before every annual meeting, to discuss possible fine-tuning of the strategy in a dedicated session;
- For the reporting period fixed by the EC, to update data to the preparation of the technical report;
- By July 2025, January 2027 and January 2028, when updated versions of this plan and the final report on activities performed must be delivered.

In any case, EUFIC will assess the KPIs before each annual meeting in order to discuss possible adjustments to the strategy with all the partners, as well as to ensure that issues and blockers for the achievement of the planned objectives and activities are spotted and managed properly in time.

9 Conclusion

This document presents the dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy and activities designed by the FoSSNet project to reach project objectives having in mind the target audiences' needs and expectations. It includes the main tools and channels that have been identified to implement the communication and dissemination process, including the partners responsible for each of them. Finally, the plan defines a management structure to guarantee the efficient implementation, tracking and assessment of the activities.

The first three months of the project were mainly dedicated to co-create with partners this plan, discussing and clarifying key elements (targets, messages to be conveyed to each target audience, etc.). Considering the urgency to start communicating and disseminating about the project and its activities, partners – particularly EUFIC – started to implement some actions during these first three months (brand identity, social media, website design and content, draft of the first press release).

The next months will represent a relevant test for the content of this document. Based on the achievements and impact monitoring between now and February 2025, the strategy presented in this plan will be evaluated and fine-tuned in order to guarantee the cost-effectiveness of activities and the achievement of the project objectives. The second and following releases of the DEC plan will likely include new actions.

Annex 1: Vision and mission process

	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4
<p>Step 1: FoSSNet core elements</p>	<p>Include, integrate, engage SSH in food system</p> <p>Inclusive Participatory/inclusive</p> <p>Individual + organisation</p> <p>Range of stakeholders</p> <p>Define & describe what is a food system scientist</p> <p>Disciplines Science/research (Academic)</p> <p>Pan-European Network</p> <p>Network</p> <p>Network</p> <p>Set of network activities</p> <p>Systems</p> <p>Holistic</p> <p>Transform the way we produce, eat, organise food</p> <p>Transformation</p> <p>Sustainable food system for all</p> <p>Vision for FS (pluralistic)</p> <p>Change</p> <p>Dynamic (change over time)</p>	<p>FSS + education</p> <p>Research education in FSS</p> <p>Research of food systems</p> <p>Network of people and networks</p> <p>Uniting networks</p> <p>Network of networks + project</p> <p>Network of researchers</p> <p>Inclusion of different actors</p> <p>Diversity of participants, perspectives, disciplines</p> <p>Varying perspectives</p> <p>European scale – multiple levels on spatial and temporal scales</p> <p>Connections to society & policy</p> <p>FSS informing policy</p> <p>Collaboration</p> <p>Collaboration driven knowledge</p> <p>Systems thinking</p>	<p>FOKIS</p> <p>Plurality</p> <p>Inclusion</p> <p>Inclusive FOKIS</p> <p>Innovation</p> <p>Network</p> <p>Research Network</p> <p>Inter/transdisc network</p> <p>Boundary setting</p> <p>Foster food systems thinking</p> <p>Knowledge</p> <p>Food system science</p> <p>Food system science</p> <p>Develop shared understanding about food system science</p> <p>Awareness</p> <p>Collaborate</p> <p>Connect</p> <p>Inclusivity</p> <p>Interdisciplinarity</p> <p>Food system transformation</p> <p>Transdisciplinary</p> <p>Empower</p> <p>Europe</p> <p>Teach</p> <p>Education</p>	<p>Collect and systematize food systems knowledge</p> <p>Food system thinking</p> <p>A system perspective is crucial for a better tomorrow</p> <p>Food systems transformation</p> <p>Systemic thinking “the big picture”</p> <p>Actionable definition of food system</p> <p>Food system science</p> <p>Facilitate food system science to local communities</p> <p>Network of networks</p> <p>Added value: being a EU network of uni/institutions</p> <p>Food policies towards sustainable food systems</p> <p>Empowerment of people involved in food systems (farmers, consumers, policymaker, industry and so on)</p> <p>A lasting science (FS) network</p> <p>Inclusive People</p> <p>Food connects our bodies with the environment</p> <p>For a healthy humanity in a healthy planet it (food) better be good</p>

<p>Step 2: The vision and mission need to consider...</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clear understanding of what food system science is - The FSS network has grown - Effective, consolidated, inclusive Pan-European network of FSS - Clear discussion in REA that "system thinking" has to be included in food science curricula - The best/excellent SSH system thinkers have a voice at FQE (?), at DG Agri, DG Sante, etc - Organisations (governments for ex) use a systems approach (e.g. nat food strategies) - Embedded in key sectors: government, industry, NGO, higher education - FS stakeholders have a say on FSS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Systems thinking + use FSS + education - Network of networks - System thinking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acknowledgement that inclusion/excl is a relevant part of FSS - The most influential network of food system thinkers - Empower future thought leaders - Mainstreaming Food Science across Europe 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - System transformation (6 votes) - Network (2 votes) - People (1 vote) - Inclusive (6 votes) - Food (4 votes)
<p>Step 3: Common vision</p>	<p>FSS thinkers are well recognized at all levels to speed up the transformation of the food system toward a socially just environmentally friendly food security</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Food system outcomes enhanced and better balanced -Provide solutions for the major questions related to the food system -Effective network of food system science and education → <u>A well developed network of FSS designed to help</u> 		<p>Building system transformation processes for people and planet</p>

		<p><u>transform FS outcomes</u></p>		
<p>Step 3: Common mission</p>		<p>-Leverage thinking to build a network of collaborative transdisciplinary scientists -Different actors collaborating together within a network to develop a new approach towards research and education in FSS leading to FS transformation <u>→ To develop a network to develop FSS to equip policy & practice to better deliver the vision</u></p>		<p>Promote system thinking and generate new relevant insights – networks of all people who can contribute to a transformation of food systems</p>

Annex 2: International days

Name	Date	Is it Annual?
International Day of Education	24 January	Yes
International Day of Women and Girls in Science	11 February	Yes
International Fact Checking day	2 April	Yes
World Creativity and Innovation Day	21 April	Yes
Europe Day	9 May	Yes
World Youth Skill Day	15 July	Yes
International Youth Day	12 August	Yes
International Literacy Day	8 September	Yes
World Food Day	16 October	Yes
International Week of Science and Peace	9 November	Yes

Annex 3: Conferences & Events relevant for the project

Name	Date
Second edition of the Food Law Academics Network conference: 'Legal issues for a sustainable agrifood chain'.	15-17 May 2024, Bari, Italy
ESOF2024: EuroScience Open Forum	12-15 June 2024, Katowice, Poland
22nd IUFoST World Congress 2024 of Food Science and Technology	8-12 Sep 2024, Rimini, Italy
Sustainable Food Systems Symposium 2024	17-18 September 2024, Göttingen, Germany
SIEF 24th Food Research Group Conference	18-20 September 2024, Budapest, Hungary
38th EFFoST International Conference 2024	12-14 November 2024, Bruges, Belgium
FOODTECHCONNECT2025: International Connect on Food Science and Technology	20-22 February 2025, Barcelona, Spain
ICEFST2025: 2 nd International Congress and Expo on Food Science and Technology	17-19 March 2025, Berlin, Germany
GFFA: Global Forum for Food and Agriculture	15-18 January 2025 Berlin, Germany
XI AESOP Sustainable Food Planning Conference "Building Movement, Achieving Transformation"	19-22 June 2024, Brussels and Ghent, Belgium
RGS-IBG Annual International Conference	27-30 August 2024, Society and Imperial College London, UK
XXX European Society for Rural Sociology Congress	To be defined